

Returns Predictability in Emerging Housing Markets

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This essay searches for a link between house prices, broad money, private credit and the macro-economy among 19 emerging markets. We also explain which variables predict the emerging markets house price index returns. The analysis consists of data for 19 emerging markets spanning the period 1966-2012. To investigate the relationship among our variables as well as the direction of the relationship, we used Fixed-Effects Panel Data Approach, Vector Auto-Regression, Granger Causality, and Variance Decomposition analysis. Using the fixed effects panel data approach, this paper analyzes the variation in 19 emerging markets house price index returns. Our results show that money market rate, growth in GDP and CPI as well as log of private credit (D) and money supply (M3) have significant predictive power on growth in house price indices a quarter ahead. There is a strong negative correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged money market rates and private credit. There is a strong positive correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged growth in GDP, CPI and log of M3. When we look at different regions, we show that in Eastern Europe only GDP has a predictive power whereas in Asia MMR, D as well as M3 has statistically significant predictive power. Granger causality tests for each country reveals strong evidence of multi-directional link between house prices, GDP, CPI, interest rates, money, and credit. House prices significantly affect the future broad money, private credit and macro variables. When we look at the variance decomposition, in almost every country we investigated, forecast errors to GDP, CPI and money market rate play an important role in explaining innovations to the house price index returns.

1. Introduction

Just like any other security, real estate investment also has its risks including falling property values, lack of liquidity, limited

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diversification and sensitivity to certain economic and financial factors. The question we are looking for is if there is evidence of a significant link among house price indices, money, credit and the macro economy. Goodhart (2007) argue that modern-style macro models are inherently non-monetary. He claims “Since there are by construction no banks, no borrowing constraints and no risks of default, the risk free short-term interest rate serves to model the monetary side of the economy. As a consequence, money or credit aggregates and asset prices play no role in standard versions of these models.”

Interest rates have direct effects on house prices. House prices appear to be associated with business-cycle movements in a number of real variables, such as consumption and investment. Researchers have not fully agreed on as to whether accommodative policy has contributed to the volatility of house or other asset prices. It can be argued that because house prices, macroeconomic and monetary variables move in response to other outside shocks hitting the economy, the direction of the relationship or the extent of causality among these variables can be difficult to point out.

The main objectives of the central banks are not necessarily in line with the goals for asset prices, particularly house prices; however house price changes can have important implications for economic activity and inflation. This effect has become especially more important since 2008 crisis. The consequences of excess changes in house prices also should be watched carefully by central banks and other government agencies that regulate financial institutions for the purpose of financial stability. Even though in the past, major declines in real house prices have often been associated with economic downturns, 2008 crises showed us that the opposite is also true; economic downturn can be caused by a decline in real house prices, especially when collateral values also decline significantly.

There is not a consensus among central banks as to how to react to excess changes in house prices. Some researchers argue that we should trust the markets therefore central banks should continue focusing on their goal of low inflation and output stability. However, there are also several researchers who claim central banks should act to prevent bubbles in house prices to avoid financial as well as macroeconomic turbulences. The question is then how should central banks respond to

movements in asset prices? There is also not a consensus on this question. Some researches advise that the price index targeted by a central bank should also include the future prices of goods and services as well as assets. Some researchers, on the other hand, argue that as long as the asset prices affect the forecast of future goods and services price inflation, they can be subject to the monetary policy. They claim central banks should respond to changes in asset prices by calculating the effect of the change in asset prices on expected inflation, and then adjusting the interest rates. Several researchers also point out that the changes in asset prices have implications for the stability of the financial sector; therefore there is an indirect relationship with monetary policy as well. If there is a bubble in asset prices, a correction might be inevitable. When the correction occurs it can be very costly to financial institutions therefore can impair the financial stability. It is clear that understanding the sources of asset price movements becomes a key element in determining the necessary monetary policy response. Hence, movements of house prices and the how these movements effect the financial sector and the macro-economy should closely be monitored by monetary authorities and financial regulators.

Using the fixed effects panel data approach, we analyze the variation in 19 emerging markets house index returns. The results show that money market rate as well as growth in GDP, Consumer Price Index, private credit and money supply have significant predictive power on growth in house price indices a quarter ahead. Using Vector Autoregression Model (VAR) methodology, the findings are expected to contribute to the evaluation of the emerging markets house price index behavior taking into consideration of several financial and economic factors.

Granger Causality tests reveal strong evidence of multi-directional causality between house prices, GDP, CPI, interest rates, money, and credit. In almost every country we investigated, forecast errors to GDP, CPI and money market rate play an important role in explaining innovations to the house price index returns.

The rest of the study is outlined as follows. Section II conducts a literature review. Section III explains the data as well as the variables used. Section IV outlines the framework of the methodology used in this study. Section V presents the conclusion of the study.

2. Literature Review

The academic studies primarily focus on the link between the housing sector and its economy. Using a vector autoregressive (VAR) model Baffoe-Bonnie (1998) tries explaining the relationship between house prices and macroeconomic key aggregates in US sub-regions. He finds that variables influence very differently across these sub-regions. Kasparova and White (2001) examine the housing markets in selected European countries using VECM. They show that effect of house prices on GDP is significantly greater than the effect of GDP on house prices. Tsatsaronis and Zhu (2004) investigate the impact of GDP, inflation and the interest rates over house prices. They show that the main reason behind the changes in house prices is the inflation hedge characteristics of residential real estate. They also show that the importance of interest rates became more obvious in the last decade of their study.

In a Federal Reserve Bank International Finance Discussion Paper (2005), Aherane et al. found that in 18 major industrial countries real house prices are pro-cyclical and they move together with real GDP, consumption, investment, CPI inflation, budget and current account balances, and output gaps. They show that house price booms are preceded by a period of easing monetary policy. After a period of rising inflation, monetary authorities begin to tighten policies before house prices peak.

Goodhart and Hoffman (2008) show that there is evidence of a significant multidirectional link between house prices, broad money, private credit and the macro economy among 17 industrialized countries. Their main results reveal that there is evidence of a significant multidirectional link between house prices, monetary variables and the macro-economy. Their results also suggest that the link between housing prices and monetary variables is stronger over more recent years and that the effects of shocks to money and credit are stronger when housing prices are booming. In a more recent study, Beltratti and Morana (2010) suggested countries that macroeconomic variables, such as interest rates and monetary aggregates, affect housing prices in G7 countries.

Asset-price volatility is believed to have been critically affected by the macro-economy (Gilchrist and Leahy, 2002). Several researches show that the housing market has a significant connection with the

performance of the overall economy and with monetary policy (Darrat and Glascock, 1989; Ball, 1994; Baffoe-Bonnie, 1998; Lastrapes, 2002; Jin and Zeng, 2004, Goodhart and Hofmann, 2008). Darrat and Glascock (1989) examined the causal relationship between money supply and real estate return and found that money supply plays an important role in changes in real estate return. Breedon and Joyce (1992) added gross financial wealth into their housing price model. They claim that money supply has a lagged effect on current real estate returns, implying a possible rejection of market efficiency. More recent studies have discussed how the relationship between money supply and asset investment leads to strong housing price fluctuation. Lastrapes (2002) used VAR model to estimate the dynamic response of housing prices to money supply shocks and interpreted these responses based on the asset view of housing demand. Jin and Zeng (2004) found that monetary policy and nominal interest rates play a significant role in the determination of housing prices, as do money shocks by generating remarkably volatile residential investment.

Kim (2005) looked at differential effects of monetary policy on housing sub-markets, specifically new home construction and existing home sales. Findings show that the existing home sale market is relatively more affected by expansionary monetary policies than is the new home construction market in the short run.

McCue and Kling (1994) examine the relationship between US equity REIT series returns and a set of macroeconomic variables. The findings indicate that nearly 60% of the variation in real estate prices is explained by the macro economy; thereby it is the nominal short-term interest rate variable that explains the majority of the real estate price movement. In a more recent study by Ewing and Payne (2005), it is found that shocks to monetary policy, economic growth, and inflation have negative impact on expected REIT returns, while on the other hand shocks to the default risk premium have positive impact on future expected returns.

Mei and Lee (1994) found the presence of a real estate factor, in addition to both a stock factor and a bond factor in asset pricing. They suggest that mutual fund managers should consider including real estate assets in their portfolios.

McMillen (2007) points out the development and increasing usage of Islamic finance for real estate funds. Ahmed (2010) looks at the global

financial crisis from an Islamic finance perspective and gives examples of real estate financing alternatives in Islamic finance. As the financial crises became global as states by Ali (2012), it started to effect Islamic banks and financial institutions as well due to their asset concentration in real estate sector.

Rahman and Shahimi (2010) show that the significant role of financing structure when controlled for macro variables does not hold for small-open developing economies like Malaysia.

Gyourko and Keim (1992) found evidence that REIT returns in the US stock market predict returns to un-securitized returns to commercial properties. They concluded that the prior year's REIT return is significant in predicting the current year's un-securitized real estate return. Myer and Webb (1993) also analyzed the lead-lag relationship using Granger causality. Their findings show that equity REITs Granger cause un-securitized real estate returns. Quan and Titman (1999) prove that real estate is positively affected by inflation as well as GDP.

Ray and Vani (2003) prove that interest rates, industrial production, money supply, inflation and exchange rates have significant affect over equity prices. Hoesli et al. (2008) present the inflation characteristics of real estate investment in the United Kingdom as well as the United States. They show a positive relationship between commercial real estate returns and expected inflation in both countries.

Schatz and Sebastian (2009) find a positive linkage between the property markets and consumer prices as well as the government bonds, while the property markets are negatively affected by the respective unemployment rates for Germany and the UK. Schatz (2009) examines the issue of whether real estate stock indices are primarily driven by the progress of property markets or by developments on general stock markets for the US and the UK. He shows that the real estate equity markets are predominantly driven by the underlying properties.

3. Data and Variables

Emerging markets house price index data for 19 Emerging Markets (see Appendix A) provided by Reidin.com; Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hong Kong Sar, Hungary, Israel, Indonesia, Lithuania, Latvia,

Mexico, Malaysia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovenia, Slovak Republic, South Africa, South Korea, Thailand, and Turkey. The sample period ranges from 1966Q1 to 2012Q2 which makes an unbalanced panel data set with a total of 906 quarters. On average there are 47 quarters per country; South Africa has the longest sample period with 186 quarters, whereas Thailand has the shortest with 18 quarters. The details of each country period are provided in the Appendix A.

The below table (Table 1) shows the summary statistics which are computed as the averages of each country i 's time-series statistics. $RE_{i,t}$ is the quarterly growth of the house price indices of 19 emerging countries provided by REIDIN.com; $GDP_{i,t}$ is the quarterly growth of GDP; $MMR_{i,t}$ is the level of quarterly Money Market Rate; $CPI_{i,t}$ is the growth of Consumer Price Index; $D_{i,t}$ is the log of private credit and $M3_{i,t}$ is the log of money supply. Panel A is the summary statistics of all 19 countries. Panel B is the summary statistics of 11 Eastern European emerging countries; Turkey, Bulgaria, Russia, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Poland. Panel C is the summary statistics of 5 Asian emerging countries; Hong Kong, Indonesia, South Korea, Malaysia, and Thailand.

Other variables are obtained from IFS and OECD. Missing variables are found from each country's central bank or other official resources. The variables that we used are; the growth of house price indices, the growth of real GDP, the growth of consumer price index, the level of the short-term nominal interest rate, the log of nominal broad money and the log of nominal private credit.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Panel A – All Countries						
Variable	RE	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3
Mean	0.017	0.012	6.208	0.014	11.012	5.841
Standard deviation	0.048	0.078	7.981	0.019	2.301	3.977
Minimum	-0.233	-0.326	0.060	-0.034	6.686	-0.704
Maximum	0.389	0.303	196.153	0.383	14.554	17.031
Observations N	906	901	904	906	713	800
Observations n	19	19	19	19	18	17
Observations T-bar	47.684	47.421	47.579	47.684	39.611	47.059
Variable	RE	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3
Panel B – Eastern Europe						
Mean	0.019	0.013	4.838	0.014	9.910	6.840
Standard deviation	0.063	0.103	10.891	0.024	1.925	2.410
Minimum	-0.233	-0.326	0.100	-0.024	6.686	3.285
Maximum	0.389	0.303	196.153	0.382	13.716	10.993
Observations N	380	379	373	380	254	330
Observations n	11	11	11	11	10	11
Observations T-bar	34.556	34.455	33.909	34.545	26.400	30.00
Panel C – Asia						
Variable	RE	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3
Mean	0.011	0.015	5.718	0.010	11.090	7.698
Standard deviation	0.038	0.071	4.332	0.013	2.561	5.685
Minimum	-0.169	-0.228	0.060	-0.034	7.136	1.450
Maximum	0.191	0.173	23.927	0.103	14.083	17.013
Observations N	268	265	270	268	234	209
Observations n	5	5	5	5	5	3
Observations T-bar	53.600	53.000	54.000	53.600	46.800	69.667

Table 1 shows the summary statistics of the country level data which are computed as the averages of each country's time-series statistics. Mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values and observation details are reported for the data set. Panel A is the summary statistics of all 19 countries. Panel B is the summary statistics of 11 Eastern European emerging countries; Turkey, Bulgaria, Russia, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Poland. Panel C is the summary statistics of 5 Asian emerging countries; Hong Kong, Indonesia, South Korea, Malaysia, and Thailand. Table 1 show that the mean growth of the 19 emerging markets house price indices is 0.017, while the growth rate is lower in Asian emerging countries; it is actually higher in Eastern European emerging countries.

The below figures (Figure 1) show the quarterly house price indices of 19 emerging markets. It is expected to see a positive trend in house price due to growing populations. Land is an important factor in housing obviously and is in fixed supply, therefore housing becomes relatively scarce, and the relative price rises. While some countries show a continuous growth in their study periods, others show busts and booms.

Figure 1: House Price Indices in Emerging Countries

These graphs display quarterly house price indices in 19 Emerging Countries

The below figures (Figure 2) show the quarterly percent change in house price indices (solid line) and the quarterly percent change in real GDP (dotted line) in 19 emerging markets.

Figure 2. House Price and GDP Growth in Emerging Countries

These graphs display quarterly percent change in house price indices (solid line) and real GDP (dotted line)

On the other hand, figure 3 shows the quarterly percent change in house price indices (solid line) and the quarterly percent change in CPI (dotted line) in our sample countries.

Figure 3. House Price and CPI Growth in Emerging Countries

These graphs display quarterly percent change in house price indices (solid line) and CPI (dotted line)

The figures reveal that, while there might be a correlation between growth in house indices and GDP as well as CPI, the relationship is not perfect at all. Growth in house prices in some countries move in the same direction with growth in GDP, However, several countries also show a deviation in the direction of this relationship. The similar pattern is also found in the relationship between the growth in house price indices and the growth in CPI in these countries. This also means that there will not be a major multicollinearity problem including these variables in our empirical model.

4. The Theoretical Framework

4.1. Predictability of House Price Index Returns

4.1.1. Parameter Estimates

The fixed-effects panel data regression shows the relationship between the House Price Index returns and the independent variables; gross domestic product (GDP), money market rate (MMR), consumer price index (CPI), private credit (D) and money supply (M3).

$$r_{j,t} = \alpha_j + \beta Z_{j,t} + \varepsilon_{j,t} \quad (1)$$

r is index return for country j at time t and independent variables for country j are defined by Z at time t .

The below table (Table 2) shows the parameter estimates and standard errors for house price index returns from the fixed effects regression results with clustered standard errors. In the regression, dependent variable is the quarterly growth on the house price indices of 19 emerging countries provided by REIDIN.com; $RE_{i,t}$. Independent variables are growth of $GDP_{i,t}$, level of Money Market Rate $MMR_{i,t}$, growth of Consumer Price Index $CPI_{i,t}$, log of private credit $D_{i,t}$ and log of money supply $M3_{i,t}$. Standard errors are reported in parenthesis. *, **, *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Table 2. Fixed Effects Panel Regressions

Constant	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3	R ²
0.294***	0.035	-0.002***	0.270***	-0.055***	0.059***	0.16
(0.079)	(0.053)	(0.001)	(0.100)	(0.016)	(0.016)	

Table 2 shows the parameter estimates and standard errors for house price index regression results. Results show that all of the coefficients, except for GDP, are statistically significant at 1% level. Money market rate, growth in CPI, private credit and M3 are all positively correlated with the growth in house price index returns. Coefficient signs also seem to be in line with the current literature on house in developed countries. Quan and Titman (1999) and Hoesli et al. (2008) found positive relationship between house returns and anticipated inflation in the US and the UK. McCue and King (1994) claim that nominal short term interest rate explains majority of the variation in house series.

4.1.2. Forecasting House Price Index Returns

To test whether house prices, credit, money and economic activity can predict one-quarter-ahead market returns in emerging countries, fixed-effects panel data regression is used.

$$r_{j,t+1} = \alpha_j + \delta X_{j,t} + \xi_{j,t+1} \quad (2)$$

r is index return for country j at time $t+1$ and independent variables for country j are defined by X at time t . The lagged dependent variable is also added as a control variable. As stated by Ferson et al. (2003), persistent dependent variables may result in a spurious regression. In panel data, the variance-covariance matrix of the error terms is simply the combination of variance-covariance matrices of each country which, aside from the autocorrelation of the error terms within each country, causes a contemporaneous cross-sectional correlation. This can inflate the t -statistics by a significant amount. To correct this, we compute standard errors in the existence of heteroskedasticity and contemporaneous cross-correlations as suggested by Rogers (1983, 1993). By estimating intercepts, α , separately for each country j , we lower to the country-level data and make sure that each country's error term is orthogonal to the explanatory variables for that country.

Therefore, in a panel data using fixed effects regression, the results reject the time-series relation between the dependent and independent variables. In equation (2), the slope coefficient, δ , together with its clustered standard errors, shows whether there is a statistically significant relation between the house price index returns and broad money, private credit and macro economy.

The below table (Table 3) shows the parameter estimates and standard errors for house price index returns from the fixed effects regression results with clustered standard errors. In the regression, dependent variable is the lead quarterly growth of the house price indices of 19 emerging countries provided by REIDIN.com; $RE_{i,t+1}$. Independent lagged variables are growth of the house price index; $RE_{i,t}$, growth of $GDP_{i,t}$, level of Money Market Rate $MMR_{i,t}$, growth of Consumer Price Index $CPI_{i,t}$, log of private credit $D_{i,t}$ and log of money supply $M3_{i,t}$. Clustered standard errors are reported in parenthesis. *, **, *** indicate significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

Table 3. Forecasting House Price Index-Fixed Effects Panel Regressions

	Constant	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3	R^2
1	0.016*** (0.003)	0.053 (0.038)					
2	0.021*** (0.003)		- (0.001)				
3	0.015*** (0.003)			(0.066)			
4	0.042* (0.024)				-0.002 (0.002)		
5	0.029*** (0.006)					-0.002* (0.001)	
6	(0.058) (0.062)	(0.024)	- (0.001)	0.216* (0.130)	- (0.011)	(0.022)	

Table 3 shows the univariate regression of the one quarter ahead house price index returns on growth of GDP, level of MMR, growth of CPI,

log of D and log of M3. Second row shows that the money market rate is negatively correlated with the future growth in house price index returns at 5% significance level with a t-statistics of -2.56 when it is regressed alone. Growth in money supply, M3, as seen in row five, is also negatively correlated with the future growth in house price index returns at 10% level with a t-statistics of -1.74 when it is regressed alone. Both variables have statistically significant predictive power. On the other hand, third row reveals that growth in CPI is positively correlated with the future growth in house price index returns at 1% level with a t-statistics of 2.67. CPI has a strong predictive power. When we regress all of the variables together, we see that all of our variables significantly predicts the growth in house price index returns. Interestingly in this setting, GDP and private credit have forecasting power so they are statistically significant as opposed to when they were regressed by themselves. The coefficient of GDP is 0.061 with a t-statistics of 2.54, whereas the coefficient of D is -0.037 with a t-statistics of -3.32. This means that when there is a positive growth in private credit, the house price indices tend to be negatively affected from this the following quarter. We explain this by the lack of organized mortgage markets in emerging markets as well as the structure of financial institutions. When private credit to businesses increase, available money to the housing markets might be declining therefore affecting the growth in prices negatively. Our results show that there is a strong negative correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged money market rates and private credit. There is a strong positive correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged growth in GDP, CPI and log of M3.

We also examine if the predictive power of these variables is different for different regions. When we do regression one quarter ahead house price index returns on our money, credit and macro variables in Eastern European emerging markets and Asian emerging markets in our sample, we actually get different results. Table 4 reveals that in Eastern Europe, only GDP has predictive power a quarter ahead at 5% significance level. The other variables are not statistically significant even at 10% level. However in Asian emerging countries, money market rate, private credit and money supply have significantly predictive power at 1% level.

The below table (Table 4) shows the parameter estimates and standard errors for house price index returns from the fixed effects regression

results with clustered standard errors. In the regression, dependent variable is the lead quarterly growth of the house price indices provided by REIDIN.com; $RE_{i,t+1}$. Independent lagged variables are growth of the house price index; $RE_{i,t}$, growth of $GDP_{i,t}$, level of Money Market Rate $MMR_{i,t}$, growth of Consumer Price Index $CPI_{i,t}$, log of private credit $D_{i,t}$ and log of money supply $M3_{i,t}$. Panel A is the fixed effects regression results of 11 Eastern European emerging countries; Turkey, Bulgaria, Russia, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Poland. Panel B is the fixed effects regression results of 5 Asian emerging countries; Hong Kong, Indonesia, South Korea, Malaysia, and Thailand. Clustered standard errors are reported in parenthesis. *, **, *** indicate significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

Table 4. Forecasting House Price Index for Different Regions

Panel A - Fixed Effects Panel Regression for Eastern Europe							
Constant	RE	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3	R²
0.140*	0.458**	0.083*	-0.001	0.261	-0.037	0.037	0.3
(0.075)	(0.079)	(0.039)	(0.002)	(0.266)	(0.034)	(0.045)	
Panel B - Fixed Effects Panel Regression for Asia							
Constant	RE	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3	R²
	0.484**	0.006	-	0.094	-	0.050**	0.4
(0.063)	(0.084)	(0.024)	(0.001)	(0.182)	(0.016)	(0.016)	

4.2. Relationship among House Prices, Credit, Money and Economic Activity

The analysis is quarterly data for 19 emerging markets spanning the period 1966-2012. To investigate the relationship among our variables as well as the direction of the relationship, we used Vector Auto-regression, Granger Causality, and Variance Decomposition analysis. The estimation of a Vector Auto-regression, VAR model, introduces by Sims (1980), requires two steps. First, a vector of variables dated at time t is regressed on several lags of itself. The residuals from these regressions are interpreted as innovations which show the new information about the variables that became available during period t . In the second step of estimation, these innovations are regressed on

themselves, using one of several statistical procedures. The second-stage regressions are often given a structural or behavioral interpretation. Therefore, the residuals from the second-stage regressions are often viewed as structural shocks.

$$Y_t = AY_{t-1} + \dots + A^k Y_{t-k} + e_t \quad (3)$$

where k is the number of lags that is considered in the system Y_t , Y_{t-1}, \dots, Y_{t-k} equals to the $1 \times p$ vector of variables and A, \dots, A^k equal to the $p \times p$ matrices of coefficients to be estimated. Also e_t is an $1 \times p$ vector of innovations that may be contemporaneously correlated but are uncorrelated with their own lagged values and uncorrelated with all of the right-hand side variables.

4.2.1. Unit Root Test

For the co-integration methodology, at least two of the series should be non-stationary process that contains a single unit root. If $Y_t \sim I(1)$, then $Z_t = Y_t - Y_{t-1}$ is stationary $I(0)$. We used Augmented Dickey-Fuller test on all of the variables for each country separately. We took first differences of all the variables that are non-stationary to make them stationary. We also used Akaike and Schwarz criterions to determine the lag lengths for each country. Estimating the six dimensional VAR at the individual country level can suffer from too few degrees of freedom especially if there is missing data which is very common for macro variables. We had to drop some of the variables in some countries to get around this problem, especially the variables that have significant missing quarterly data.

4.2.2. Granger Causality Test

In a regression analysis, we look at the dependence of one variable on other variables, but it does not necessarily show the causation. In other words, the existence of a relationship between variables does not prove causality or the direction of the influence.

Granger (1969) developed a test approach to prove that a time series X contribute to the prediction of another series, Y . In this section the relationship among house price index returns, GDP, inflation, money

market rate, private credit and money supply are investigated using Granger Causality tests.

Table 5 displays the results from the Granger causality tests for each country, which reveals strong evidence of multi-directional causality between house prices, GDP, CPI, interest rates, money, and credit. In Hong Kong, Lithuania, Mexico and Poland, for example, the relationship between house prices and GDP is in both directions; GDP has a significant effect on the future house prices and house prices also have significant effect on the future GDP. This multi-directional relationship also exists between CPI and house prices in Hong Kong and Lithuania. There is also a multidirectional link between MMR and house prices in Czech Republic, South Africa and South Korea. Finally in Czech Republic the direction of relationship between private credit and house prices is bi-directional.

The below table (Table 5) shows the direction of granger causality tests conducted in each country. ΔREI is the growth of the house price index; ΔGDP is the growth of GDP; MMR is the level of Money Market Rate; ΔCPI is the growth of Consumer Price Index, ΔD is the log of private credit, and $\Delta M3$ is the log of money supply. P values are in parenthesis.

Table 5. Granger Causality Test

$\Delta\text{GDP} \rightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$	$\Delta\text{REI} \rightarrow \Delta\text{GDP}$	$\Delta\text{GDP} \leftrightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$
Hong Kong (0.09)	Bulgaria(0.01)	Hong Kong
Lithuania (0.01)	Estonia (0.04)	Lithuania
Mexico (0.02)	Hong Kong (0.01)	Mexico
Poland (0.08)	Lithuania (0.01)	Poland
	Mexico (0.07)	
	Poland (0.01)	
	Russia (0.01)	
	Slovak Republic (0.01)	
	South Africa (0.01)	
	Turkey (0.01)	
$\Delta\text{CPI} \rightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$	$\Delta\text{REI} \rightarrow \Delta\text{CPI}$	$\Delta\text{CPI} \leftrightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$
Hong Kong (0.09)	Hong Kong (0.01)	Hong Kong
Hungary (0.04)	Indonesia (0.03)	Lithuania
Latvia (0.04)	Lithuania (0.01)	
Lithuania (0.09)	Slovak Republic (0.01)	
Mexico (0.02)	South Korea (0.01)	
	Thailand (0.05)	
$\text{MMR} \rightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$	$\Delta\text{REI} \rightarrow \text{MMR}$	$\text{MMR} \leftrightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$
Czech Republic (0.09)	Bulgaria (0.01)	Czech Republic
Estonia (0.09)	Czech Republic (0.09)	South Africa
Israel (0.01)	Hungary (0.04)	South Korea
South Africa (0.02)	South Africa (0.01)	
South Korea (0.02)	South Korea (0.02)	
	Turkey (0.04)	
$\Delta\text{M3} \rightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$	$\Delta\text{REI} \rightarrow \Delta\text{M3}$	$\Delta\text{M3} \leftrightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$
Hong Kong (0.01)	Czech Republic (0.01)	
	Malaysia (0.01)	
$\Delta\text{D} \rightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$	$\Delta\text{REI} \rightarrow \Delta\text{D}$	$\Delta\text{D} \leftrightarrow \Delta\text{REI}$
Czech Republic (0.01)	Bulgaria (0.01)	Czech Republic
Indonesia (0.07)	Czech Republic (0.03)	
	Hong Kong (0.04)	
	Lithuania (0.02)	
	Russia (0.04)	

It is also interesting to see that in almost every country, house prices significantly affect the future broad money, private credit and macro variables. This has an important implication for the policy makers in these countries as well as the potential investors to those countries. Central banks do not necessarily implement policies to influence the future house prices, however, our results show that their policies can actually influence future house prices as well as the house prices strongly influence future broad money and private credit growth levels.

4.2.3. Variance Decomposition

In order to decompose the variance of each element of Y_t in equation 3 into components due to each of the elements of the error term and to do so for various horizons, we conduct variance decomposition analysis. In this analysis we are trying to see how much of the variance of each element of Y_t is due to the first error term and how much due to the second error term and so on.

Our findings show an interesting picture for 19 emerging markets. Table 6 presents that the forecast errors of house price index returns are mainly attributable to their own innovations in Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, and South Africa in the following quarter. However, in Israel, only 33% is attributable to its own innovation whereas 38% of the forecast error variance is explained by the innovations in CPI. In Estonia, Indonesia, Israel, Poland and Thailand less than 60% of the forecast errors are explained by their own innovations. Interestingly in Poland, innovations in CPI explain more than 46% of the forecast error variance to house price index returns. When we look at the second quarter horizon in table 6, also in Hong Kong, Lithuania, Malaysia, Mexico, Russia and Turkey less than 60% of the forecast errors are explained by their own innovations. In almost every country we investigated, forecast errors to GDP, CPI, and money market rate play an important role in explaining innovations to the house price index returns.

The below table (Table 6) shows the variance decomposition of house index growth in each country. REI is the growth of the house price index; GDP is the growth of GDP; MMR is the level of Money Market Rate; CPI is the growth of Consumer Price Index, D is the log of private credit, and M3 is the log of money supply.

Table 6. Variance Decompositions

Period	S.E.	REI	GDP	MMR	CPI	D	M3
Bulgaria							
1	0.024157	100	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.031711	81.0747	5.530402	6.061027	2.8238	4.50706	0.003009
3	0.050675	77.97421	2.21586	16.83344	1.196401	1.778603	0.001487
Czech Republic							
1	0.022201	100	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.047523	93.13504	5.120865	0.066697	0.051782	1.552998	0.072618
3	0.069225	78.24086	16.86071	0.053422	0.535702	4.23035	0.078966
Estonia							
1	0.063735	58.78516	12.78755	28.14462	0.282668	0	0
2	0.072426	45.53605	13.55422	34.58357	2.245882	0.031937	4.048342
3	0.078737	39.14124	14.80916	33.80846	8.379692	0.366971	3.49448
Hong Kong							
1	0.030106	74.99744	0.032971	11.88576	13.08383	0	0
2	0.047896	55.13629	0.039506	19.81967	16.62758	4.372861	4.004098
3	0.058281	43.70027	4.087707	23.19794	13.441	8.984462	6.588625
Hungary							
1	0.017843	68.89523	2.423627	9.406063	19.27508	0	0
2	0.018313	68.53662	2.482223	9.586204	18.3672	0.944833	0.082918
3	0.018922	67.36271	3.044674	10.54692	17.83996	0.890909	0.31482
Indonesia							
1	0.006904	39.00586	2.743775	7.785134	50.46524	0	0
2	0.008069	30.1889	4.633825	5.815601	53.88642	5.466183	0.009081
3	0.009158	23.55779	5.625276	14.42514	42.0328	14.18964	0.169355
Israel							
1	0.014088	33.45416	9.106639	19.20721	38.23199	0	0
2	0.016441	31.44371	11.93171	23.14612	31.18132	1.155003	1.142133
3	0.018134	28.46376	14.22682	25.15489	27.11396	4.055117	0.985443
Latvia							
1	0.102881	84.92258	12.07714	0.173257	2.827026	0	0
2	0.105802	80.32982	11.71405	0.257026	7.699099	0	0
3	0.106228	79.75319	11.73884	0.404214	8.103748	0	0
Lithuania							
1	0.077673	71.85774	11.79486	0.394036	15.95337	0	0
2	0.085396	59.73515	14.2033	0.704092	21.855	3.502454	0
3	0.098347	51.58357	19.48563	7.959546	18.30758	2.663678	0
Malaysia							
1	0.035419	62.15115	24.48083	4.723128	8.644898	0	0
2	0.044953	47.3974	37.29059	3.076149	12.11371	0	0.122148
3	0.045099	47.09465	37.06453	3.121785	12.10755	0	0.61148
Mexico							
1	0.009546	70.06695	0.004049	28.69054	1.238463	0	0
2	0.01064	56.39961	7.084196	24.06984	10.19012	0	2.25623
3	0.011372	51.64943	8.238863	24.71749	13.01386	0	2.380353

Poland							
1	0.040745	21.6541	4.496019	27.24993	46.59995	0	0
2	0.048746	24.75313	9.648047	28.18578	37.32417	0	0.088874
3	0.060885	28.26724	8.110692	28.71206	32.15057	0	2.759436
Russia							
1	0.037977	70.56521	18.56186	0.485193	10.38773	0	0
2	0.043642	53.50575	16.19698	0.778594	25.58018	0.951301	2.987207
3	0.047568	51.42839	14.07409	0.907194	21.53531	0.871043	11.18397
Slovak Republic							
1	0.018012	100	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.025347	99.76028	0.061759	0	0.177958	0	0
3	0.034925	98.68466	0.204	0	1.111337	0	0
Slovenia							
1	0.032443	100	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.036588	96.74549	1.225553	0	0.116883	0	1.912072
3	0.037587	94.26179	3.09955	0	0.141117	0	2.497541
South Africa							
1	0.012137	99.64917	0.17224	0.101014	0.077571	0	0
2	0.017433	93.58635	0.125583	3.793401	0.13879	1.380478	0.975399
3	0.020111	86.71716	0.576669	7.915657	0.37984	2.996521	1.414152
South Korea							
1	0.013546	85.33999	10.33327	0.045611	4.281133	0	0
2	0.017821	65.14771	22.9192	7.732547	3.763197	0.126361	0.310983
3	0.022263	47.89443	24.49571	17.4917	4.504618	5.40568	0.207866
Thailand							
1	0.009175	14.88978	0.444163	19.9962	64.66986	0	0
2	0.011393	11.03682	32.17626	14.41466	42.37226	0	0
3	0.011833	11.06525	30.71152	13.85177	44.37147	0	0
Turkey							
1	0.013866	84.12949	0.001894	6.342265	9.526354	0	0
2	0.0273	54.16049	1.609169	4.251012	39.63942	0	0.339912
3	0.034881	41.07273	1.133549	5.608226	51.90887	0	0.276629

5. Concluding Comments

Housing market is undoubtedly one of the most important components of a national economy. This is also true for emerging countries. However, there is not enough empirical evidence regarding their interaction with money, private credit and macro economy. Central banks are not necessarily primarily interested in movement of asset prices, particularly house prices; however house price changes can have important implications for economic activity and inflation. The consequences of substantial changes in house prices should also be watched carefully by central banks and other government agencies that

regulate financial institutions for the purpose of financial stability. 2008 crises showed that the house prices have important effects on the overall economy. Emerging markets have been relatively less affected by this crises compared to the developed markets.

Using the fixed effects panel data approach, this paper analyzes the variation in 19 emerging markets house index returns. Our results show that money market rate, growth in GDP and CPI as well as log of private credit (D) and money supply (M3) have significant predictive power on growth in house price indices a quarter ahead. There is a strong negative correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged money market rates and private credit. There is a strong positive correlation between the growth in house price indices and the lagged growth in GDP, CPI and log of M3. When we look at different regions, we show that in Eastern Europe only GDP has a predictive power whereas in Asia MMR, D as well as M3 has statistically significant predictive power.

Granger causality tests for each country reveals strong evidence of multi-directional link between house prices, GDP, CPI, interest rates, money, and credit. House prices significantly affect the future broad money, private credit and macro variables. When we look at the variance decomposition, in almost every country we investigated, forecast errors to GDP, CPI and money market rate play an important role in explaining innovations to the house price index returns.

Findings of this study may have important implications over the macro and monetary policies of the emerging markets. There has been a dramatic increase in REIT funds in the last decade. Emerging markets REIT funds also have become important tool in investments. Since the underlying asset of REITs are the house prices, finding variables that have important implications in a lead-lag relationship can also have important implication on these funds. Empirical findings of this paper do not necessarily support this analysis therefore a future research on the variables we investigated and REITs can present important implications for investors on more liquid assets like REITs.

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Appendix A.

Monthly Data	Starting Date	Ending Date
HONG KONG SAR	Jan-93	May-12
ISRAEL	Jan-01	Apr-12
KOREA	Jan-86	Jun-12
THAILAND	Mar-08	May-12
SOUTH AFRICA	Jan-66	Jun-12
TURKEY	Jun-07	Jun-12
Quarterly Data	Starting Date	Ending Date
BULGARIA	1997Q1	2012Q2
CZECH REPUBLIC	2004Q1	2010Q4
ESTONIA	2003Q3	2012Q1
HUNGARY	2001Q4	2012Q2
INDONESIA	2002Q1	2012Q2
LITHUANIA	1998Q4	2012Q1
LATVIA	2006Q1	2012Q1
MEXICO	2005Q1	2012Q1
MALAYSIA	2005Q1	2012Q1
POLAND (5 MISSING OBSERVATIONS)	2002Q4	2012Q1
ROMANIA	2009Q1	2012Q1
RUSSIA	2001Q1	2012Q1
SLOVENIA	2007Q1	2012Q1
SLOVAK REPUBLIC	2005Q1	2012Q1